

Towards Digital Agriculture: IoT Connectivity through a Multilayer NTN

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Abstract—Digital agriculture, enabled by technologies like the Internet of Things (IoT), necessitates robust and efficient connectivity solutions to become a reality, especially in rural and remote regions where terrestrial network infrastructure falls short. This paper introduces a novel 3D network architecture, which encompasses two layers of Non Terrestrial Networks (NTN): the first NTN layer includes drones, while the second one is made by a constellation of Low-Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites. The proposed drone layer allows optimizing communication between IoT devices and LEO satellites, by improving reliability, increasing throughput, and reducing packet queuing time. Using preliminary simulation results, we show the potential of the proposed multilayer NTN architecture to support IoT data collection for precision agriculture applications.

Index Terms—IoT, NTN, drone, satellite, digital agriculture.

I. INTRODUCTION

The global demand for sustainable agricultural practices has increased due to the intertwined pressures of population growth, climate change, and resource scarcity. Digital agriculture, leveraging the Internet of Things (IoT), has emerged as a transformative approach, which by integrating sensors with edge and cloud computing, among other technologies, can optimize productivity and minimize the use of natural resources. However, one of the main bottlenecks remains connectivity, particularly in rural and remote areas, where the lack of a basic terrestrial communication infrastructure prevents access and thus adoption of IoT applications.

Recent advances in NTN, particularly LEO satellites, have provided a promising foundation for enhanced connectivity for digital agriculture. The rapid increase in the number of LEO satellite launches, driven by companies such as SpaceX, OneWeb, and Amazon Kuiper, has significantly expanded the global satellite infrastructure. These constellations, designed primarily to provide low-latency, high-bandwidth connectivity, cater to a wide range of real-time applications [1, 2]. Beyond these general-purpose deployments, specific LEO constellations have emerged to support IoT traffic. For example, technologies such as LoRa are integrated into satellite-based IoT systems to enable efficient low-power communication. Companies such as LacunaSpace, EchoStar,

Fig. 1: Multilayer NTN IoT vs Direct Satellite IoT

and Plan-S exemplify this trend by offering direct IoT services that deliver ubiquitous IoT connectivity through their dedicated satellite networks.

However, direct communication between IoT devices and satellites can face practical limitations, such as intermittent visibility, high energy consumption at the device level, and increased latency during signal acquisition and handover in densely populated constellations [3]. To address these limitations, this paper proposes a novel 3D NTN architecture that introduces drones as an intermediary layer between IoT devices and LEO satellites.

II. NTN MULTI-LAYER ARCHITECTURE

This paper introduces a drone-assisted architecture for satellite-enabled IoT networks, with a focus on its application in precision agriculture. The proposed system leverages drones to implement various store-and-forward policies, increasing data throughput and enhancing network availability through multiple flight operations. By addressing the challenges of intermittent satellite visibility and limited device energy capacity, the architecture provides a robust solution for agricultural use cases such as crop health monitoring, irrigation management, and pest control, in rural remote areas. This work advances the development of drone-assisted NTNs, demonstrating the potential of such systems to address connectivity gaps in digital agriculture.

The IoT landscape includes diverse communication technologies such as NB-IoT and LoRa/LoRaWAN, each tailored to specific use cases. NB-IoT, a cellular-based technology, excels in providing high reliability and wide coverage, but requires more complexity and cellular infrastructure. In contrast, LoRa/LoRaWAN

Fig. 2: Feasibility Test (Top View); A Raspberry-Pi LoRaWAN Gateway is mounted on a drone to collect and store packets over a test case area in Luxembourg.

operates in unlicensed spectrum, offering long-range communication with low power consumption, making it ideal for remote and energy-sensitive applications. Although these technologies differ in operational parameters, both aim to enable efficient IoT connectivity for large-scale deployments.

The proposed NTN multilayer architecture is designed to be agnostic to the underlying IoT protocol, supporting both NB-IoT and LoRa/LoRaWAN seamlessly. For simplicity, this work assumes LoRa/LoRaWAN as the IoT communication protocol. As depicted in Figure 1, the architecture leverages drones equipped with LoRaWAN gateways to bridge the ground IoT layer and the satellite layer. The ground IoT layer has been implemented and evaluated as depicted in Figure 2: IoT sensors are deployed in a field in Luxembourg. A Raspberry Pi LoRaWAN gateway was mounted on a Phantom drone to collect data from the sensors. The data is stored and can be forwarded to the remote server, once the satellite is available. This protocol-agnostic design allows for easy adaptation to other IoT technologies such as NB-IoT. For example, by replacing the LoRaWAN gateway with an eNodeB on the drone, it is possible to enable NB-IoT connectivity without requiring fundamental changes in architecture.

A. Data Collection Modes

To accommodate various application requirements and optimize communication accordingly, the proposed architecture supports three distinct data collection modes. These modes leverage the interaction between drone flights and satellite visibility. They are described hereafter, and they are illustrated in Figure 3.

Mode A - Sequential Flight Mode - In this mode, the drone performs multiple flights over the agricultural area, collecting and decoding data from the IoT devices during each pass. The data collected are stored onboard the drone until a LEO satellite becomes visible. Once satellite connectivity is established, the drone forwards the stored data to the satellite for further processing.

Fig. 3: Data Collection Modes

This mode is ideal for areas with infrequent satellite visibility, ensuring that all is collected prior to transmission.

Mode B - Satellite Adjacent Mode - This mode synchronizes drone flights with the upcoming satellite visibility windows. The drone starts its flight shortly before the satellite appears in its communication range. After gathering and decoding data from IoT devices, the drone forwards the collected data to the satellite immediately after completing the data collection phase. This mode minimizes data storage requirements on the drone while optimizing the timing of data transfers.

Mode C - Direct Relay Mode - In this mode, the drone operates during periods of simultaneous satellite visibility. As the drone collects data from IoT devices, it directly forwards the data to the satellite without intermediate storage. This mode supports near-real-time data relays and is suitable for delay-sensitive applications.

The flexibility of these communication modes ensures that the architecture can adapt to varying environmental conditions, satellite visibility patterns, and operational needs, providing a robust solution for data-driven digital agriculture in remote and underserved regions. It has to be noticed that Modes A and B require the implementation of a local LoRaWAN network server on the drone to decode packets which are locally stored, before being forwarded to the LEO satellite.

B. Benefits

The inclusion of drones in multilayer NTN-IoT architectures simplifies communication and reduces device-level complexity. Acting as intermediaries between IoT devices and LEO satellites, drones enable the use of standard terrestrial hardware, removing the need for high-gain antennas, specialized frequency bands, or costly hardware upgrades. This architecture mitigates the challenges posed by the significant link budget required for direct satellite communication, while avoiding frequency interference issues. Furthermore, the closer proximity of drones to IoT devices facilitates lower spreading factors and reduced transmission power in LoRa-based systems, significantly reducing energy consumption and communication overhead [4]. Such a design is particularly advantageous for large-scale IoT deployments, where minimizing device adaptations ensures cost-effectiveness and scalability.

Fig. 4: Drone Trajectory in the selected test area in Luxembourg, with 780 seconds of drone flight.

Drones also improve network reliability and availability. With flexible flight capabilities, they compensate for the limited visibility windows of LEO satellites, providing extended communication opportunities. This ensures improved packet delivery ratios (PDR) and increased IoT data collection without requiring adjustments to device configurations.

C. Challenges

Despite their benefits, drones introduce new challenges. IoT devices must adapt to the dynamic availability of drones, necessitating precise awareness of flight schedules to prevent packet drops. In addition, effective scheduling mechanisms are required to handle collisions during drone communication windows, as their intermittent availability adds complexity.

While similar challenges exist with direct satellite communication, the integration of drones adds further coordination demands across terrestrial devices and NTN network elements. Ensuring seamless transmission and minimizing disruptions require advanced scheduling algorithms and real-time synchronization mechanisms tailored to the dynamic nature of multilayer NTN IoT systems.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

To evaluate the proposed architecture, we consider a scenario in which a LoRaWAN gateway is mounted on a drone operating in Mode A, performing several flights prior to the satellite's visibility for data forwarding. During these flights, the drone receives packets from IoT devices within its coverage area and temporarily stores them until satellite connectivity is established. The trajectory of the drone, as illustrated in Figure 4, spans the Echternach region in Luxembourg, covering an area of approximately 2.5 km x 1.5 km. Within this field, 50 IoT devices are randomly distributed, simulating a scenario in which the exact positions of the devices are not predetermined. The drone follows a flight pattern designed to traverse the entire field systematically, ensuring coverage of the entire deployment area regardless of the specific locations of the IoT devices. Future optimizations in this work will incorporate the

actual spatial distribution of the devices to further refine and optimize the flight pattern.

The simulation environment, implemented in Python, models the interactions between key entities, including IoT devices, drones, and LEO satellites, while capturing the dynamics of the physical communication layer. The simulation tracks various performance metrics, such as packet drops, collisions, and successfully collected packets. The data packets collected are forwarded to the satellite layer when the satellites pass within the drone communication range, reflecting a real-world data handling flow in such a network configuration. This framework ensures a detailed assessment of the multilayer NTN IoT architecture and provides a foundation for future enhancements.

The test environment consists of 50 IoT devices deployed randomly across the region, each transmitting packets periodically using a spreading factor of 12 ($SF = 12$). Two different transmission scenarios were examined: one with devices that transmit every 10 minutes and another every 30 minutes. The evaluation was carried out over a 24-hour period, during which the drone completed 10 flights. For satellite communication, LACUNASAT 2B and LACUNASAT 3 were used as test satellites, both operating at an altitude of approximately 500 kilometers. Satellite visibility was calculated using orbital parameters obtained from the Celestrak online TLE (Two-Line Element) source.

To introduce randomness and minimize collisions, the IoT devices initiated transmissions at random intervals between 10 and 30 minutes. When the link budget for establishing a packet transmission is sufficient, the simulator evaluates potential packet drops and collisions by considering the availability of the drone and overlapping transmissions from other packets. A packet drop occurs when a device transmits while the drone is out of range or not in flight. Packet collisions, on the other hand, occur when multiple devices transmit simultaneously within overlapping physical layer resources, causing interference that prevents successful packet reception.

Once the drone receives the packets, they are stored until a satellite becomes visible. During the satellite visibility window, the drone uploads the stored packets using a forward link protocol. The simulator assumes a session setup time of 10 seconds and an upload speed of 1 Kbps for satellite communication. This process is repeated until the end of the 24 hour test period.

As shown in Figure 5a, the total number of received packets increases proportionally to the number of drone flights. Additionally, the number of received packets is higher in the 10-minute transmission scenario due to the increased transmission frequency. However, as illustrated in Figure 5b, the packet delivery ratio (PDR) is lower in the 10-minute scenario because of the higher occurrence of packet drops and collisions. This

(a) Received Packets vs Drone Flight Frequency

(b) PDR vs Drone Flight Frequency

Fig. 5: Network performance metrics.

highlights a trade-off between increased data throughput and reduced energy and network efficiency.

The findings suggest that a packet scheduling technique is essential to optimize transmission timing, reduce collisions, and improve reliability. Furthermore, compared to a direct satellite IoT configuration, where average satellite visibility is limited to approximately two minutes, the use of drones provides extended connectivity and improved network throughput. This advantage is amplified by the drone’s ability to maintain consistent communication links during its flights, enhancing energy efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and minimizing the need for hardware upgrades on IoT devices. The results also reveal that some packets fail to reach the satellites due to the absence of satellite visibility following the drone’s final flight within the test period. This underscores the importance of scheduling drone flights in accordance with the visibility windows of the satellite.

IV. CONCLUSION

Our proposed 3D NTN architecture introduces an innovative approach to enhance IoT connectivity in rural and remote areas, specifically tailored to the needs of digital agriculture. Using drones as a dynamic intermediary layer between ground IoT devices and LEO satellites, this architecture overcomes key limitations of direct IoT-to-LEO communication, including high latency and inconsistent network availability. Simulation results validate the efficacy of the drone layer in increasing data collection reliability, improving frequency of

communication, and lowering both energy consumption and hardware demands for IoT devices.

The capability of drones to dynamically reposition within deployment zones enhances network visibility, contributing to higher PDR and improved data collection. This is especially critical in dense IoT networks, where the short visibility windows of LEO satellites, typically limited to a few minutes per orbital pass, create substantial barriers.

However, challenges arise under high-frequency transmission conditions, as packet drops and collisions increase. This emphasizes the necessity for intelligent scheduling mechanisms to manage communication opportunities effectively and ensure fair bandwidth allocation between devices. Without such mechanisms, energy efficiency and system reliability may degrade, particularly in high-density deployments with intensive data demands.

Future efforts should prioritize the development of adaptive scheduling algorithms that capitalize on the unique features of this multilayer architecture. These algorithms must address dynamic factors such as IoT traffic patterns and drone mobility, while optimizing transmission timing to enhance PDR and reduce collisions. In doing so, the architecture could achieve greater scalability and reliability, solidifying its transformative impact on IoT applications in agriculture and beyond.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was supported by COMECT European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Program under grant agreement no. 101060881, AGRIOS AFR FNR project, no. 18013466, and ESA SatNEX INVENTIVE project, no. 4000130962/20/NL/NL/FE.

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